

1 **HELB is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.**

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5 We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and
6 at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here discovery/identification of *HELB* as a
zygotic cell factor required or important during the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.

7 Citations

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9 1. Tkáč, J., Xu, G., Adhikary, H., Young, J.T., Gallo, D., Escibano-Díaz, C., Krietsch, J., Orthwein,
10 A., Munro, M., Sol, W. and Al-Hakim, A., 2016. HELB is a feedback inhibitor of DNA end resection.
11 Molecular cell, 61(3), pp.405-418.